

NDAC/LO/064

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13th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP3000-4000: IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator (Lindegren)

Based on discussions at the Copenhagen meeting in June, some remarks on these processes and their interface with the Set Solutions were made in the note NDAC/LO/060 (= C). Results from the preprocessing of the 2nd and 3rd ESTEC IDT counts simulation runs (April and June 1985) have been summarized in LO/061-062 (= C , C). They indicate a satisfactory performance of the chosen algorithm (using 45 bins) also for the very faintest stars (< 100 photons/frame).

WP6000-7000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren, Söderhjelm)

No work to be reported.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

A software package has been set up to simulate input data for the Double Star process. The IDT counts pertaining to a given object are generated frame-by-frame and preprocessed. The output consists of the signal parameters etc for each frame containing the object (some 1500 frames for the full 2.5 years). The simulations take into account the following effects in particular:

- object model with n point sources (currently just n independent single stars - each defined by its five parameters)
- scanning model including realistic deviations from nominal
- IFOV piloting model with systematic and random depointing as well as the stepwise control
- IFOV (payload) profile extending over the whole field (enables to study also veiling glare if required)
- field-to-grid transformation and OTF model (field and colour dependent I_0 , M_1 , M_2 , M_3 and corresponding phases)
- Poisson noise
- preprocessing with 45 bins

A second part of the package (under development) will analyse the Fourier components of the signal and in particular determine the astrometric and binary parameters by direct least-squares fit.

Working papers

- C Lindegren 1985-06-17: Notes on the IDT Preprocessing and RGO/DSRI (NDAC/LO/060) interface
- C Lindegren 1985-06-19: Results of IDT Preprocessing Simulations (NDAC/LO/061)
- C Lindegren 1985-08-30: Preprocessing of ESTEC IDT photon count (NDAC/LO/062) runs (3)
- C Lindegren 1985-09-05: Derivation of the Starmapper geometry (NDAC/LO/063) in field coordinates